

This is the title of the scientific poster

Author's name can be added here¹

¹Along with affiliations

Introduction

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Results

Type your text or add figures here

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Discussion

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Methodology

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Acknowledgments

This work was supported in part by funding provided by Brain Canada, in partnership with Health Canada, for the Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform initiative.

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